

Synthesis, characterization, thermal, catalytic and antimicrobial aspects of Ln^{III} polymers of phenolic resins

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Abstract : Inorganic compounds of transition and inner transition metal ions play an important role in various chemical reactions. Calcium and lanthanides are similar in their chemical behavior, but nature has selected only calcium in various biochemical processes. Therefore Ln^{III} metal ions inorganic coordination polymers have been selected for the study of antimicrobial and catalytic activity. In coordination polymers superior behavior of united inorganic and organic moiety is observed as catalyst. It is superior to pure organic or inorganic material alone. Coordination polymers of HEAP-1,3-BD poly[(2-hydroxy-4-ethoxy acetophenone)-1,3-butylene] with La^{III}, Pr^{III}, Nd^{III}, Sm^{III}, Gd^{III}, Tb^{III} and Dy^{III} metal ions have been synthesized and characterized by elemental analyses, electronic spectra, magnetic susceptibilities, FTIR, NMR, Scanning Electronic Microscopy (SEM) and thermogravimetric analyses. The metal ligand ratio is 1 : 2 in all the coordination polymers. High thermal stability of coordination poly chelates indicates their polymeric nature. Catalytic activity of selected coordination polymers was studied for important organic synthesis. It is found that polymer metal chelate complexes are efficient and effective catalyst in the Biginelli three component, one-pot synthesis of 3,4-dihydropyrimidin-2(1H)-ones. Antimicrobial activity of isolated Ln^{III}-coordination polymers against *Escherichia coli*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Staphylococcus aureus* (bacteria) and *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* (yeast) were measured. In compared to resin, polymer metal chelate complexes showed better antimicrobial activity. It was observed from the study that the Ln^{III}-coordination polymers act as an efficient and effective catalysts and antimicrobial agents.

The coordination polymers can be used as an economical and eco-friendly catalysts for selected organic synthesis with different aldehydes and β -ketoesters.

Keywords : Coordination polymer, catalysts, antimicrobial study, thermal study.

Introduction

A coordination polymer is composed of synthetic polymer and metal ions, where the polymeric ligands are bounded to metal ions by coordinate covalent bond. A polymer ligand contains anchoring sites like nitrogen, oxygen or sulphur obtained either by polymerization of monomer possessing the coordinating site or by a chemical reaction between a polymer and a low molecular weight compound having coordinating ability. The synthesis results in an organic polymer with inorganic functions. Day by day, society is in need of a variety of materials. Therefore, different types of new processes are established and modifications are made in old processes to get desired materials. Society is very conscious about environment-

friendly relationship in atmosphere and climate change. Chemistry is playing a vital role in daily life. Hence utmost care is necessary in establishing and modifications of chemical processes.

The metal atoms attached to polymer backbone are bound to exhibit characteristic catalytic behavior^{1,2}, which is distinctly different from their low molecular weight analogue. Indeed, many synthetic coordination polymers have been found to possess high catalytic efficiency, in addition to bioinorganic industry³, wastewater treatment⁴, pollution control, hydrometallurgy, thermal, anionic poly-electrolyte hydrogels, semiconductivity, heat resistance and biomedical potentials⁵⁻¹⁰.

In the present work catalytic activity of Ln^{III}-coordi-

nation polymers for pharmaceutical important compounds have been reported, in addition to their antimicrobial activity. It is found that polymeric ligand possess good thermal stability, while coordination polymers are thermally less stable. Coordination polymers have good catalytic and bactericidal activities compared to the parent polymeric ligand. Thus, lanthanides(III) coordination polymers have significant potential as a catalyst for organic transformations and antimicrobial agents.

Experimental

Chemicals required :

2-Hydroxy-4-ethoxyacetophenone (HEAP), 1,3-butanediol (1,3-BD) (Aldrich), polyphosphoric acid

(Lancaster) (PPA), methanol, ethanol, acetone (AR grade), hydrated metal acetates of lanthanum, praseodymium, neodymium, samarium, gadolinium, terbium and dysprosium (Merck), dimethylsulfoxide (DMSO), benzaldehyde, 4-hydroxybenzaldehyde, 4-chlorobenzaldehyde, vanillin, urea, acetoacetic ester, acetyl acetone (AR grade), nutrient-broth (Hi-media, M 002) and MGY media (Hi-media).

Synthesis of resin and polychelates :

Acetophenone based polymeric ligand was synthesized by Friedel-Craft polycondensation reaction using 2-hydroxy-4-ethoxy acetophenone (10.8 g, 0.06 mole), 1,3-butanediol (5.38 mL, 0.06 mole) and polyphosphoric acid (PPA) (20 g) as a catalyst (Scheme 1). The coordination

Scheme 1. Synthesis and reaction mechanism of monomer and resin.

polymers of synthesized ligand with La^{III}, Pr^{III}, Nd^{III}, Sm^{III}, Gd^{III}, Tb^{III} and Dy^{III} were prepared using method as reported earlier¹¹. The resin was solid, brown in color, D.P. > 270 °C, yield 9.12 g (84.51%). All the coordination polymers are insoluble in common organic solvent such as methanol, acetone, chloroform, benzene, toluene *etc.* while, soluble in dimethylformamide, dimethylsulfoxide and tetrahydrofuran. The polychelates were blackish brown in color and yield obtained was in the range 1.63–1.71 g (65–75%).

HEAP-1,3-BD :

IR (KBr) : 3200–3400 (-OH stretching), 2950–2880 (-CH₂ stretching), 2730 (intra mol H bond), 1590, 1560, 1525, 1490 (-C=C-aromatic), 1345 (-OH), 1260 (Ar-O-R), 890, 690 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) : δ 12.04 (s, phenolic OH), 4.05 (2H, q), 1.41 (3H, t), 1.26 (3H, t, bridge), 2.35 (2H, t, bridge), 2.97 (2H, t, bridge), 3.02 (1H, m, bridge), 7.68–7.65 (1H, Ar-H).

M[(HEAP-1,3-BD)₂.2H₂O]_n :

IR (KBr) : 3200–3500 (-OH stretching), 2950–2880 (-CH₂ stretching), 1610–1645 (>C=O), 1600–1540, 1470–1600 (-C=C-aromatic), 1350–1340, 1265 ± 10, 670–650, 565, 459–480 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) : δ 4.14–4.06 (2H, q), 1.45–1.41 (3H, t, bridge), 1.30–1.27 (3H, t, bridge), 2.40–2.36 (2H, t, bridge), 3.02–2.97 (2H, t, bridge), 3.07–3.03 (1H, m, bridge), 7.71–7.69 (1H, Ar-H).

Synthesis of substituted 3,4-dihydropyrimidin-2(1H)-ones :

All substituted 3,4-dihydropyrimidin-2(1H)-ones were synthesized by following method. Benzaldehyde, 4-hydroxybenzaldehyde, 4-chlorobenzaldehyde, vanillin, urea, acetoacetic ester and acetyl acetone were used to synthesize 3,4-dihydropyrimidin-2(1H)-ones.

In a typical reaction a solution of β-ketoester (0.1 mole), aldehyde (0.1 mole) and urea (0.1 mole) in ethanol (40 mL) was refluxed in presence of metal polychelate as a catalyst, to give 3,4-dihydropyrimidin-2(1H)-ones as shown in Scheme 2. The reaction mixture was then allowed to cool; crude product was obtained. The product was separated by filtration. The crude product was dissolved in ethanol and filtered to remove insoluble catalyst and recrystallized. The separated catalyst can be reused giving simple water treatment after drying.

5-(Ethoxycarbonyl)-4-phenyl-6-methyl-3,4-dihydropyrimidin-2(1H)-one :

IR (KBr) : 3232, 3103, 2932, 1732, 1639, 1590, 1461, 1413, 1341, 1316, 1283 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃ + DMSO-*d*₆) : δ 1.15 (3H, t), 2.35 (3H, s), 4.09 (2H, q), 5.25 (1H, d), 5.65 (1H, s, NH), 7.20–7.46 (5H, Ar-H), 9.23 (1H, s, NH).

5-(Ethoxycarbonyl)-4-(4-chlorophenyl)-6-methyl-3,4-dihydropyrimidin-2(1H)-one :

IR (KBr) : 3461, 3250, 3125, 2983, 2928, 1717, 1706, 1654, 1570, 1491, 1462, 1386 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃ + DMSO-*d*₆) : δ 1.19 (3H, t), 2.25 (3H, s), 2.30 (3H, s), 4.01 (2H, q), 5.43 (1H, d), 6.42 (1H, s, NH), 7.20–7.44 (4H, Ar-H), 8.58 (1H, s, NH).

5-(Ethoxycarbonyl)-4-(4-hydroxyphenyl)-6-methyl-3,4-dihydropyrimidin-2(1H)-one :

IR (KBr) : 3441, 3288, 3126, 2921, 1703, 1651, 1619, 1494, 1423, 1391, 1360, 1318, 1261, 1236, 1144, 1093, 1015, 968, 831 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃ + DMSO-*d*₆) : δ 1.05 (3H, t), 2.55 (3H, s), 2.31 (3H, s), 4.09 (2H, q), 5.49 (1H, d), 8.32 (1H, s, phenolic OH), 6.28 (1H, s, NH), 6.81–7.31 (4H, Ar-H), 8.19 (1H, s, NH).

Scheme 2. Synthesis of 3,4-dihydropyrimidin-2(1H)-ones.

5-(Ethoxycarbonyl)-4-(4-hydroxy-3-methoxyphenyl)-6-methyl-3,4-dihydropyrimidin-2(1H)-one :

IR (KBr) : 3445, 3293, 3125, 2921, 1701, 1645, 1619, 1489, 1423 cm^{-1} ; $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3) : δ 2.27 (3H, s), 1.1 (3H, t), 3.98 (2H, q), 3.77 (3H, s, OCH_3), 5.20 (1H, d), 6.86–7.11 (3H, Ar-H), 7.59 (1H, s, NH), 9.46 (1H, s, NH), 8.38 (1H, s, phenolic OH).

5-Acetyl-4-phenyl-6-methyl-3,4-dihydropyrimidin-2(1H)-one :

IR (KBr) : 3284, 3126, 2918, 1703, 1643, 1618, 1494, 1427, 1389, 1361, 1315, 1278, 1235, 1146, 1099, 1018, 968, 833 cm^{-1} ; $^1\text{H NMR}$ ($\text{CDCl}_3 + \text{DMSO}-d_6$) : δ 2.10 (3H, s), 2.29 (3H, s), 5.28 (1H, d), 5.27 (1H, s, NH), 7.22–7.47 (5H, Ar-H), 9.20 (1H, s, NH).

5-Acetyl-4-(4-chlorophenyl)-6-methyl-3,4-dihydropyrimidin-2(1H)-one :

IR (KBr) : 3442, 3289, 3126, 2919, 1702, 1641.5, 1619, 1491, 1425, 1388, 1364, 1314, 1262, 1237, 1142, 1092, 1015, 967, 837 cm^{-1} ; $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3) : δ 2.26 (3H, s), 2.32 (3H, s), 5.05 (1H, d), 7.38 (1H, s, NH), 7.26–7.6 (4H, Ar-H), 9.28 (1H, s, NH).

5-Acetyl-4-(4-hydroxyphenyl)-6-methyl-3,4-dihydropyrimidin-2(1H)-one :

IR (KBr) : 3373, 3256, 3116, 2965, 2920, 1702, 1681, 1669, 1609, 1449, 1425, 1388, 1364, 1314, 1262 cm^{-1} ; $^1\text{H NMR}$ ($\text{CDCl}_3 + \text{DMSO}-d_6$) : δ 2.19 (3H, s), 2.32 (3H, s), 5.03 (1H, d), 7.39 (1H, s, NH), 7.06–7.38 (4H, Ar-H), 9.26 (1H, s, NH), 8.62 (1H, s).

5-Acetyl-4-(4-hydroxy-3-methoxyphenyl)-6-methyl-3,4-dihydropyrimidin-2(1H)-one :

IR (KBr) : 3444, 3290, 3126, 2922, 1704, 1641, 1621, 1491, 1425 cm^{-1} ; $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3) : δ 2.08 (3H, s), 2.35 (3H, s), 3.83 (3H, s, OCH_3), 5.23 (1H, d), 6.69–6.85 (3H, Ar-H), 8.69 (1H, s, NH), 7.26 (1H, s, NH), 8.94 (1H, s, phenolic OH).

Thermogravimetric study :

Thermal measurements were carried out on a DuPont thermal analyzer in nitrogen atmosphere at a heating rate of $10\text{ }^\circ\text{C min}^{-1}$. The water content at $25\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and cumulative weight loss data of the polymeric ligand and its polychelates at 100, 150 and $200\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ is given in Table 1.

Preparation of microbial culture :

The antimicrobial activity of resin and its polychelates

was checked against *Escherichia coli*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Staphylococcus aureus* and yeast strains *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*. The antimicrobial effect of compound was investigated by standard microbiological parameters using agar diffusion method¹². The concentration of the compound tested for the antimicrobial activity was 500 ppm during the experiment. The bacterial culture was maintained on N-agar (N-broth, 2.5% w/v agar). The yeast culture was maintained on MGYB in 3% (w/v) agar.

For inoculum developments of bacterial and yeast culture, a loop of cell mass from previously grown slants was inoculated into sterile N-broth tubes containing 15 ml medium and incubated on a shaker at 150 rpm and $37\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 24 h, to obtain sufficient cell density (i.e. 1×10^8 cells/ml).

Sterile, melted N-agar was initially inoculated with respective cultures and poured into a sterile empty petriplate and allowed to solidify. A ditch was prepared with the help of a sterile scalpel on opposite ends, with one for control (solvent without compound) and the other for the test sample. To find the minimum inhibitory concentration, all the cultures were tested for different concentration of compound ranging from 50–1000 ppm. There after, the plates were transferred to the refrigerator for 10 min to allow the sample diffuse out from the ditch and into the agar before organisms start growing followed by incubation at $37\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 24 h. Next day the distance in millimeter (mm), from the ditch was measured as a parameter of inhibition.

Media composition :

For the growth and test of bacteria and yeast, the N-broth and MGYB media were used. The composition used is as shown below.

N-broth : Peptone 0.6% (6.0 g), NaCl 0.15% (1.5 g), beef extract 0.15% (1.5 g) were dissolved in 1 L distilled water and pH was adjusted to 6.7–7.3.

MGYP : Malt extract (3.0 g), glucose (10.0 g), yeast extract (3.0 g) and peptone (5.0 g) were dissolved in 1 L distilled water and pH was adjusted to 5.5.

Analytical procedures :

Elemental analysis of carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen was carried out on a Coleman C, H, N analyzer (Table 2). The metal content was determined by complexometric

Table 1. Water content at 25 °C and cumulative weight loss data of the polymeric ligand and its polychelates at 100, 150 and 200 °C

Compd.	H ₂ O at 25 °C		Found					
			100 °C		150 °C		200 °C	
	g	%	g	%	g	%	g	%
{[La(HEAP-1,3-BD) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂].OH} _n	36.00	5.47	12.83	1.95	22.96	3.49	61.54	9.35
{[Pr(HEAP-1,3-BD) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂].OH} _n	36.00	5.45	18.39	2.77	24.17	3.66	72.19	10.93
{[Nd(HEAP-1,3-BD) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂].OH} _n	36.00	5.43	12.39	1.87	21.01	3.17	66.03	9.96
{[Sm(HEAP-1,3-BD) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂].OH} _n	36.00	5.38	14.85	2.22	24.82	3.71	70.18	10.39
{[Gd(HEAP-1,3-BD) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂].OH} _n	36.00	5.33	14.18	2.10	21.27	3.15	73.08	10.82
{[Tb(HEAP-1,3-BD) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂].OH} _n	36.00	5.31	17.55	2.59	23.59	3.48	64.41	9.55
{[Dy(HEAP-1,3-BD) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂].OH} _n	36.00	5.28	13.77	2.02	21.01	3.08	72.14	10.58

n = 1 considered for calculation of formula weight of resin and coordination polymer.

Table 2. Analytical data of the polymeric ligand and its polychelates

Compd.	Formula weight of repeating unit	Yield (g) (%)	Analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)	
			M	C
			(HEAP-1,3-BD) _n [C ₁₄ H ₁₈ O ₃] _n	234
{[La(HEAP-1,3-BD) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂].OH} _n	658	1.71 (73.11)	21.79 (21.09)	57.44 (51.07)
[C ₂₈ H ₃₉ O ₉ La] _n				
{[Pr(HEAP-1,3-BD) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂].OH} _n	660	1.66 (71.10)	22.05 (21.33)	57.27 (50.92)
[C ₂₈ H ₃₉ O ₉ Pr] _n				
{[Nd(HEAP-1,3-BD) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂].OH} _n	663	1.67 (71.54)	22.40 (21.73)	57.04 (50.66)
[C ₂₈ H ₃₉ O ₉ Nd] _n				
{[Sm(HEAP-1,3-BD) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂].OH} _n	669	1.71 (73.24)	23.14 (22.44)	56.45 (50.20)
[C ₂₈ H ₃₉ O ₉ Sm] _n				
{[Gd(HEAP-1,3-BD) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂].OH} _n	676	1.70 (72.83)	23.95 (23.23)	55.84 (49.69)
[C ₂₈ H ₃₉ O ₉ Gd] _n				
{[Tb(HEAP-1,3-BD) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂].OH} _n	678	1.63 (69.97)	24.17 (23.42)	55.73 (49.56)
[C ₂₈ H ₃₉ O ₉ Tb] _n				
{[Dy(HEAP-1,3-BD) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂].OH} _n	682	1.69 (72.28)	24.65 (23.82)	55.35 (49.30)
[C ₂₈ H ₃₉ O ₉ Dy] _n				

HEAP-1,3-BD = Poly[(2-hydroxy-4-ethoxy acetophenone)-1,3-butylene].

n = 1 considered for calculation of formula weight of resin and coordination polymer.

titrations with standard Na₂EDTA¹³ after decomposing the polychelates with a mixture of concentrated hydrochloric, sulfuric and perchloric acids in a 5 : 2 : 3 mL ratio, respectively. Magnetic susceptibilities were measured using Gouy method at room temperature. FTIR spectra were recorded over the 4000–400 cm⁻¹ range on a Perkin-Elmer infrared spectrophotometer model 938 by using KBr pellets. ¹H NMR spectra were recorded on Bruker 400 MHz NMR spectrometer using DMSO-*d*₆ as a solvent. Thermal measurements were carried out on a

Du Pont thermal analyzer in nitrogen atmosphere at a heating rate of 10 °C/min.

Results and discussion

HEAP-1,3-BD polymeric ligand was prepared by polycondensation of 2-hydroxy-4-ethoxyacetophenone and 1,3-butanediol in acidic medium. The structure of polymeric ligand and its coordination polymers were determined by FTIR (Fig. 1), ¹H NMR and elemental analysis. Micro-analytical data of the polymeric ligand and its coordina-

Fig. 1. IR spectra of polychelates of HEAP-1,3-BD resin.

tion polymers are presented in Table 2. The slight deviation in the elemental analysis results may be due to polymeric nature of the compounds, as the value of the end groups were not taken into account for the theoretical calculations. The analysis of the polymeric ligand indicates that the molar ratio of 2-hydroxy-4-ethoxy-

acetophenone and butanediol is 1 : 1. The micro-analytical data showed that the HEAP-1,3-BD and metal acetates were in a 1 : 2 ratio in all the coordination polymers. The nature of the ligand, high thermal stability and metal ligand ratio (1 : 2) suggests their polymeric nature⁸. Analytical data suggests that, all the coordination polymers contains two water molecules, which is supported by the TGA results (Schemes 3a and 3b).

where, M = La^{III}, Pr^{III}, Nd^{III}, Sm^{III}, Gd^{III}, Tb^{III} and Dy^{III}
 Scheme 3a. Proposed geometry of the polymeric chelate.

FTIR spectra :

The important FTIR bands of HEAP-1,3-BD resin (Scheme 4) and its coordination polymers are given below. The FTIR spectrum of M-HEAP-1,3-BD showed a broad and strong band around 3200–3400 cm⁻¹ suggesting the presence of coordinated water molecules. The presence of coordinated water molecules in the complex was further conformed by the appearance of bands in the region 1600–1540 cm⁻¹ for δ (HOH) deformation and 670–650 cm⁻¹ for the rocking modes of coordinated water. Furthermore, a weak band around ~2700 cm⁻¹ indi-

Scheme 3b. Proposed cluster of the polymeric chelate.

Scheme 4. Proposed structure of the polymeric ligand.

cates presence of an intramolecular hydrogen bond in parent resin. The intramolecular bond is possible between the oxygen of carbonyl group and hydrogen of hydroxyl group, which disappears due to deprotonation in polychelates. Two strong bands appeared at 2950–2880 cm^{-1} due to the asymmetric and symmetric stretching vibrations of the $-\text{CH}_2$ groups. The $-\text{C}=\text{O}$ stretching frequency in the resin is observed around 1590 cm^{-1} , appearing at a lower frequency of 15 to 20 cm^{-1} in all the polychelates, which suggests $-\text{C}=\text{O} \rightarrow \text{M}$ coordination. The band around 890–1903 cm^{-1} may be attributed to the 1,2,3,4,5-penta substituted phenyl ring, which suggest that the linkage in the resin chain occurs through 3 and 5 positions of the monomer. The strong bands observed around the $1260 \pm 10 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ region is attributed to the $\text{Ph}-\text{O}-\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_3$ ether linkage. The bands in the around 1490 cm^{-1} region are attributed to $-\text{C}=\text{C}-$ stretching (aromatic) vibrations. In the polychelates the bands observed around 459–480 and 565 cm^{-1} indicate the $\text{M}-\text{O}$ bond, suggesting that phenolic and carbonyl groups are involved in bond formation with the metal ion.

The FTIR spectrum of 5-(ethoxycarbonyl)-4-phenyl-6-methyl-3,4-dihydropyrimidin-2(1*H*)-one shows a sharp and broad band in the 3500–3200 cm^{-1} region. In this region two bands due to asymmetric and symmetric ν ($\text{N}-\text{H}$) are generally observed near 3450 and 3250 cm^{-1} respectively. While the band around 1730 cm^{-1} is assign to $>\text{C}=\text{O}$ stretching vibrations. The bands in the 1450–1600 cm^{-1} are due to aromatic vibration. The band around 3100–3000 cm^{-1} is assign to $\text{C}-\text{H}$ stretching vibrations of aromatic ring. Two bands in the region of 1360–1310 cm^{-1} is assigned to $\text{C}-\text{N}$ stretching vibrations. The band in the region of 2940–2850 cm^{-1} is due to asymmetric and symmetric stretching vibrations of $-\text{CH}_2$ group. In a similar manner bands obtained for other Biginelli compounds are assigned.

^1H NMR spectra :

The ^1H NMR signals of poly[(2-hydroxy-4-ethoxy acetophenone)1,3-butylene] (HEAP-1,3-BD) and polychelates (M-HEAP-1,3-BD) are presented below.

HEAP-1,3-BD resin shows signals at δ 12.04 ppm due to $-\text{OH}$ group *ortho* to $(\text{CH}_3-\text{C}=\text{O})$ and δ 7.68–7.65 ppm due to aromatic ring protons, respectively. The signal at δ 2.35–3.02 ppm appears, due to the presence of $(\text{CH}_3-\text{C}=\text{O}-\text{Ar}-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_2)$ -bridge protons. While triplet and quadrate signals at δ 1.41 ppm and δ 4.05 ppm are assigned to $-\text{CH}_2-$ and $-\text{CH}_3$ protons of ethoxy group, respectively. In all the polychelates the signal of the $-\text{OH}$ group is completely disappeared, indicates that the bond formation takes place through the $-\text{OH}$ *ortho* to $(\text{CH}_3-\text{C}=\text{O})$.

The NMR spectrum of 5-(ethoxycarbonyl)-4-phenyl-6-methyl-3,4-dihydropyrimidin-2(1*H*)-one shows signal at δ 1.17 ppm (3H, t) is assigned to CH_3 protons of $-\text{OC}_2\text{H}_5$ group. Signal at δ 4.07 ppm (2H, q) is assigned to $-\text{CH}_2$ protons of $-\text{OC}_2\text{H}_5$ group. Signal at δ 2.35 ppm is assigned to $-\text{CH}_3$ protons. While the signal at δ 5.28 ppm (1H, d) is assigned to the CH protons of hetero ring. The signals at δ 5.67 and 9.20 ppm values are assigned to both $-\text{NH}$ protons respectively. While the signals at δ 7.22–7.47 ppm values are assigned to aromatic ring protons. In a similar manner signals obtained for other Biginelli compounds are assigned.

Scanning electron microscopy of HEAP-1,3-BD ligand and its coordination polymers :

To understand the structural study of the synthesized polymeric ligand and its coordination polymers, Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM), an effective tool has been used extensively. SEM of the pure polymeric ligand was carried out to understand their inner morphology and pore structure. The morphology of fracture surface for the polymeric ligand clearly shows their porous nature as shown in Fig. 2a. SEM of the polymeric ligand shows a fringed model of the crystalline-amorphous structure. The fringes represent transition state between the crystalline and amorphous phase¹⁴. The polymeric ligand exhibits more amorphous character with closed packed surface having deep pits. While the surface topology of the coordination polymer shows a stiff morphology compare to that of the polymeric ligands, indicating that the interaction of the metal ion with the polymeric ligand filled up the pores of the polymeric ligands as shown in Fig. 2b. The surface of the coordination polymers appears quite

Fig. 2a. SEM of HEAP-1,3-BD resin.

Fig. 2b. SEM of HEAP-1,3-BD-Sm polychelate.

uniform but presence of some holes and cracks are observed which may be due to air.

Catalytic study :

3,4-Dihydropyrimidin-2(1*H*)-ones and their derivatives are important class of compounds due to their diverse therapeutic and pharmacological applications. Many functionalized derivatives of 3,4-dihydropyrimidin-2(1*H*)-ones are known to act as anti-hypertensive agents, alpha-antagonists, neuropeptide-Y (NPY) antagonists and also serve as integral backbones of several calcium channel blockers¹⁵. Several marine alkaloids containing the 3,4-dihydropyrimidin-2(1*H*)-ones units are found to exhibit pharmacological activities and an antimicrobial activity of lanthanide chelates has great significance, due to greater biological and clinical aspects^{16,17}. Moreover, several marine alkaloids with interesting biological activities con-

tain the dihydropyrimidine-5-carboxylate moiety. Hence, this family of compounds received a great significance in their synthesis. This reaction was first reported by Biginelli in 1893, but suffers from low product yield, specially with substituted aromatic aldehydes. Subsequently several modifications were reported for the Biginelli condensation reaction to improve the yield. The Biginelli reaction was carried out employing many reagents such as lanthanum chloride, manganese acetate, montmorillonite KSF, silica-supported sulfuric acid and metal triflates¹⁸⁻²⁰. Most of these reported catalysts possess various drawbacks such as stringent reaction conditions; tedious work-up procedures, long reaction times, use of stoichiometric amounts of catalysts and some of the catalysts employed are expensive.

In recent years, the development of more economical and environmental friendly conversion processes is gaining interest in the industry and chemical technology. In continuation of our interest to develop metal based catalysts, we intended to find efficient, practically viable, environmentally benign and high yielding method for the Biginelli three component, one-pot synthesis of 3,4-dihydropyrimidin-2(1*H*)-ones using selected Nd^{III} and Sm^{III} polychelates.

To study the efficiency and effectiveness of the catalyst, selected reactions were studied using Nd^{III} and Sm^{III} coordination polymers under similar conditions to synthesize the 3,4-dihydropyrimidin-2(1*H*)-ones and results are summarized in Tables 3 and 4. It is found that Nd^{III} and Sm^{III} coordination polymers are giving excellent re-

Table 3. Synthesis of substituted 3,4-dihydropyrimidin-2(1*H*)-ones, catalyzed with Nd^{III} polychelate

Product	R	R ¹	Time (h)	Yield (%)	m.p. (°C)	
					Found	Reported
a	C ₆ H ₅	OE _t	2	90	202	202-204
b	4-OH-C ₆ H ₅	OE _t	4	88	199	199-200
c	4-OH-3-OMe-C ₆ H ₅	OE _t	6	88	208	208-211
d	4-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	OE _t	5	90	213	213-214
e	C ₆ H ₅	Me	2	91	231	234-235
f	4-OH-C ₆ H ₅	Me	4	88	209	210-211
g	4-OH-3-OMe-C ₆ H ₅	Me	6	89	244	246-248
h	4-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	Me	5	88	215	215-216

Table 4. Synthesis of substituted 3,4-dihydropyrimidin-2(1*H*)-ones, catalyzed with Sm^{III} polychelate

Product	R	R ¹	Time (h)	Yield (%)	m.p. (°C)	
					Found	Reported
a	C ₆ H ₅	OEt	2	89	202	202–204
b	4-OH-C ₆ H ₅	OEt	4	88	200	199–200
c	4-OH-3-OMe-C ₆ H ₅	OEt	6	90	210	208–211
d	4-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	OEt	5	91	212	213–214
e	C ₆ H ₅	Me	2	87	233	234–235
f	4-OH-C ₆ H ₅	Me	4	91	210	210–211
g	4-OH-3-OMe-C ₆ H ₅	Me	6	88	247	246–248
h	4-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	Me	5	93	215	215–216

sults for all the synthesis studied. The yield obtained was more than 90%, time required for completion of the reaction was less and the FTIR and ¹H NMR data of compounds were compatible with the proposed structures as well as the melting points were in accordance with those reported in the literature, which is acceptable as per the present standard.

The used Nd^{III} and Sm^{III} coordination polymers for the synthesis of 3,4-dihydropyrimidin-2(1*H*)-ones and its derivatives were found to be insoluble in organic solvents, therefore, it can be easily recovered and reused. They are also stable at high temperature, non-toxic and non-hazardous too. Therefore, these catalysts are cost-effective and eco-friendly and act as an efficient and effective catalyst for Biginelli one-pot synthesis.

Antimicrobial activity of resin and polychelates :

The polymeric ligand and their coordination polymers were studied for their antimicrobial activity against standard bacterial strains of *Escherichia coli*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Staphylococcus aureus* (bacteria) and *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* (yeast). The compounds were tested at different concentrations ranging from 50–1000 ppm, to find out the minimum concentration of the ligand and polychelates, which inhibits the microbial growth. The minimum concentration 500 ppm was found. The inhibition of growth from the ditch was measured in millimeter (mm) and the results are shown in Table 5. The polymeric ligand was found biologically active and their coordination polymers showed significantly enhanced antibacterial activity against one or more bacterial species, in comparison to the uncomplexed polymeric ligand. It is known that chelation tends to make the ligands act as more potent bactericidal agents, than the parent ligand. The antimicrobial activities of the compounds increase after chelation. Chelation reduces the polarity of the central metal ion by partial sharing of its positive charge with the donor groups²¹, increasing lipophilic nature of the central metal ion, which in turn favours its permeation to the lipid layer of the membrane. Other factors, viz. stability constant, molar conductivity, solubility and magnetic moment, are also responsible for increase in the antimicrobial activity of the coordination polymers²².

Table 5. Antimicrobial activity data of the polymeric ligand and its polychelates

Ligand/Polychelates	Zone of inhibition ^a (mm)			
	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>B. subtilis</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>S. cerevisiae</i>
(HEAP-1,3-BD) _n	–	–	–	10
{La(HEAP-1,3-BD) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂ }.OH} _n	17	21	20	23
{Pr(HEAP-1,3-BD) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂ }.OH} _n	18	22	14	21
{Nd(HEAP-1,3-BD) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂ }.OH} _n	17	19	21	22
{Sm(HEAP-1,3-BD) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂ }.OH} _n	19	20	22	23
{Gd(HEAP-1,3-BD) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂ }.OH} _n	16	18	19	21
{Tb(HEAP-1,3-BD) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂ }.OH} _n	15	21	21	22
{Dy(HEAP-1,3-BD) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂ }.OH} _n	16	23	22	23
DMSO ^b	–	–	–	–

^a16–23 mm = significantly active; 10–15 mm = moderately active; < 10 mm = weakly active. ^bSolvent (negative control).

Conclusion

It has been observed that Ln^{III}-coordination polymers act as an effective and efficient catalyst in the synthesis of pharmaceutically most important class of organic compounds. The obtained yield and quality of 3,4-dihydropyrimidin-2(1*H*)-ones and their derivatives were found excellent. The insertion of metal ion in the polymeric ligand enhances antimicrobial activity significantly against *Escherichia coli*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Staphylococcus aureus* (bacteria) and *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* (yeast). Thus, coordination polymers can be used as antifungal and antifouling coatings.

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